

WHAT WOULD OTHER EMERGENCY STROKE TEAMS DO?

Using explainable machine learning to understand variation in thrombolysis practice

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What is the problem?

Thrombolysis is a proven treatment to reduce disability risk from stroke, but carries a small risk of severe intracerebral haemorrhage. There remains a substantial between-hospital variation in thrombolysis use among patients in England and Wales who arrive at hospital within 4 hours of known stroke onset. Thrombolysis use (2016 to 2018) in all emergency arrivals ranged from 1% to 28% between hospitals, and ranged from 7% to 49% for patients arriving within 4 hours of stroke onset.

The question?

How much of this variation in thrombolysis rates is accounted for by differences in patient populations, and how much by differences in clinical practice between sites?

Method: training a machine learning model to predict who would receive thrombolysis at each hospital

The model was based on 88,928 patients arriving within 4 hours of stroke onset at 132 emergency stroke units in England and Wales, as recorded in the national stroke audit, SSNAP. An Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) machine learning model, coupled with a SHAP explainability model, was used to predict which patients would receive thrombolysis at each hospital.

When tested on independent data, the model predicted individual thrombolysis decisions with 85% accuracy, and predicted stroke team thrombolysis with an average absolute error of 1.1 percentage points (r-squared = 0.98).

SHAP values reveal the relationship between patient characteristics and model outcome

SHAP values show the contribution of patient features to the prediction made by the XGBoost model. These are expressed as change in log-odds of receiving thrombolysis due to any particular feature value.

General patterns revealed were that the odds of thrombolysis:

- Reduced 20 fold over the first 100 minutes of arrival-to-scan time.
- Varied 30 fold depending on stroke severity.
- Reduced 3 fold with imprecise onset time.
- Fell 5 fold with increasing pre-stroke disability.
- Fell 5 fold if the patient was taking anticoagulant medication.

The effect of hospital attended on the odds of receiving thrombolysis

The mean SHAP value for hospital identification shows the effect a hospital has on the odds of a patient receiving thrombolysis, after taking into account other patient features affecting the odds of receiving thrombolysis.

The odds of receiving thrombolysis varied 15 fold between hospitals, after adjustment for patient characteristics.

Conclusions

Our study of the most influential factors behind the substantial and persistent variation in thrombolysis practice between UK hospitals shows that the majority of variation arises from differences in patient selection between sites, rather than from differences in patient populations.

For further details of this work please see the paper, online book, and interactive web app (adjust patient characteristics and see the probability each team would give that patient thrombolysis).

Paper

<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/23969873231189040>

Online Book

https://samuel-book.github.io/samuel_shap_paper_1

Web App

https://stroke-predictions.streamlit.app/Thrombolysis_decisions